

Justice : Conceptual Dimensions

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Justice is one of the important objectives of the state. One of the earliest treaties on politics, Plato's 'Republic' was an attempt to construct a just state. Justice was its central concept. Justice is reconciler and synthesizer of political values and as said by Aristotle it is 'What answers to the whole of goodness.' Conception of justice changes with the passage of time. Therefore what was justice in the past, may be injustice in the present and vice-versa. Thus there have been the egalitarian perception of justice where the highest place is accorded to the values of equality, the 'libertarian' perception in which the liberty is the execution of God's will. The hedonist makes 'the greatest good of the greatest number' the criterion of justice: to the 'harmonizer' justice is the harmonizing of different elements and values to produce a satisfactory balance. Some identify justice with 'duty' or with maintenance of peace and order: others view it as an elitist function. Therefore justice concerns the right of the individual as well as social order of society. It is legal as well as moral at the same time. Summingly speaking it an ethical concept. Roman lawyers integrated the ideas of natural justice with the positive law of the state. As such, the civil law and the law of the nations are in conformity with the law of nature. This seems to be an abstract jurisprudence, justice lies in the enforcement of the positive law. Both law and justice seek to sustain social order. John Austin tells the law has to function as an instrument of justice on the one hand and function as an instrument to suppress mischief, on the other.

Symbolically justice is portrayed as blind folded because it is supposed to be impartial. It means there must not be any discrimination between two extremes i.e. rich or poor, high or low. Thus impartiality becomes the precondition to justice does it reflect the absence of discrimination at all?

Plato and Aristotle argued for a 'different interpretation of justice', "proportionate equality with the idea of righteousness". The philosophical interpretation of justice takes an empirical direction at the hands of Aristotle who says. "Injustices arises when equals are treated unequally". It means that if in a democratic regime, there is the discrimination on the basis of sex, it would mean treating the equals unequally. Also it would be unfair to pit heavy weight wrestler against the lightweight one. It means justice requires discrimination on the basis of differences, which is relevant to the functions performed. Platonic justice also implied that the life of people should conform to the rule of functional specialization. Here, justice becomes another name for the principal of proper station i.e. a man should practice one thing only to which his nature is best adopted. This has both individual and social aspects. The highest good of both individual and the society is conserved, if we take it for granted that there is nothing better for a man than to do a work that he is best fitted to do.

Normally, the law does not interfere in instances of discriminatory treatment in private life, but if it causes social harm, the state would be justified in interfering in it, like in instances of untouchability, where some groups are denied human rights. Thus a law against it would be just. Also the separate facilities accorded can not be truly equal. That is why Dr. Ambedkar demanded the right of entry to temples for scheduled castes and opposed the idea of separate temples, schools or hostels for them. The idea proposed by Aristotle regarding justice, led the foundation of distributive justice. According to him justice is either corrective or distributive: former implies remedy for the wrong while latter implies equal distribution among equals.

Idea of justice put forth by Marx in the post-revolutionary socialist society is from 'each according to his ability to each according to his work'. Other political economists like J.W. Chapman seeks to integrate the idea of justice with his principles of 'economic rationality

of man and consumer's sovereignty coupled with the individual claim of 'moral freedom'. According to him first principle of justice is the distribution of benefits, which Maximise benefits in accordance with the principle of consumer' sovereignty. The second principle has been criticised on the ground that the material will being of a few is purchased at the expense of many. It implies that justice requires that no one shall gain at the expense of another. Distributive justice is subjected to the condition of general welfare. It demands that the state of national economy be reshaped in a way that the benefits are made available to the common man. Thus the idea of economic justice comes to imply a socialistic pattern of society. The first objective of economic justice is to provide employment, food, shelter to every able- bodied citizen. It has been truly said that freedom is meaningless if it prevents the achievement of economic justice. Therefore the liberals believe that economic justice can be attained in the society if the state provides welfare. Services and there is progressive system of taxation a fair return for work provision of social security like old age pension, gratuity etc.

Marxian notion of justice has its origins in the area of economics. Marx believes that positive law of the state is imposed on its members by the authority of the class, which controls the means of production. According to him, law is determined by the interests of the ruling class. Interest of the working class will only be reflected when the system of private property is abolished. Thus the element of justice depends upon the class controlling the means of production. Justice will be achieved without any economic origin. Once the state withers away.

Modern liberals have since long given up the doctrine of economic laissez –fair. Redistributive justice is an integral part of revisionist liberalism as advocated by J.W. Chapmen, John Rawls and Arthur Okun.

Social justice relates to the balance between an individual's rights and social control ensuring the fulfilment of the legitimate expectations of the individual under the existing laws and to ensure him benefits and protection against any encroachment on his rights.

With the decline of the notion of the Laissez-faire, a new awareness has developed that the rights of an individual should be reasonably restricted in the interest of community because the ends of social justice require reconciliation of individual rights with that of community interest. It also presumes that in case of conflict between an individual interest and community interest, the interest of the latter must prevail. Thus we can say that social justice constitutes public good or community interest. With the gradual penetration of democracy in to the social and economic spheres, community interest has come to encompass not only the political but also the social and economic. Therefore social justice has broad spectrum ranging from the protection of minority political rights to the abolition of untouchability and the eradication of poverty. As such in the backward countries of the world, the idea of social justice enjoins upon the state to make concerted efforts for the improvement of the downtrodden and weaker sections of the society. Social justice is utilized to denote organization of society on the basis of ideas of fairness and equality current at time. It seeks a revision of social order so as to have a more egalitarian society when. Aristotle spoke of 'distributions justice', he had reformatory or what Raphael calls 'prosthetic' justice in mind, because its aim was to modify the status quo.

The affirmation of the idea of social justice is well contained in the interpretation of Dean Roscoe Pound who presents as six-fold illustration of social interests and lays down eight rural Postulates of erasure social justice. Therefore, the idea of social justice envisage to promote the welfare of the people by securing a just social order.

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